

MARINE MICROBIAL SLICK GEMS

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ABSTRACT

Marine bacteria produce Exopolysaccharides (EPS) as a stratagem for progression, adhesion to solid surfaces, and survival in harsh environments. The EPSs form a protective barrier around the cell, guarding it from extremes in temperature and salinity. These produced EPS by marine bacteria possesses diverse structure-physicochemical properties, which can be exploited as immune-modulatory and anti-viral agents, for bone-regeneration and therapy, as cicatrizing molecules, in foodstuff and bakery as thickening and gelling soup. Apart from these biotechnological application, most unique EPS are monosaccharide and linear polysaccharide from marine origin have potential application in sustainable agriculture; specifically as suppressing agent for soil-borne plant diseases, promoting plant growth, and acting as a phytopathogen, biocontrol agent, manufacturing bio-waste, waste-water treatment and as chelating agent for elimination of heavy metals.

Keywords: Exopolysaccharides; Marine bacteria; Sustainable development; Heavy metal; Oil recovery and mining

INTRODUCTION

Marine bacteria such as *Falsibacillus albus* GY10110, *Paenibacillus oceani* IB182363, *Salinimonas sediminis* N102, *Alteromonas spp.*, *Sclerotium rolfsii*, *Schizophyllum commune*, *Halomonas maura*, *Haloferax mediterranei*, *Halomonas ventosae*, *Halomonas alkaliantarctica*, *Hahella chejuensis*, *Sinorhizobium meliloti*, *Alcaligenes faecalis* and *Aureobasidium*

pullulans are famous for their proven ability to produce various exopolysaccharides. For instance, *Thiobacimonas profunda* JLT2016 had a number of transporter systems that were involved in the export of carbohydrates, carboxylic acids, amino acids, peptides, metals, and other nutrients. JLT2016 has a lot of exporters that are involved in polysaccharide, heavy metal, and metabolite efflux outside of their cells (Torres et al., 2019).

Figure 1. RAST-Genome analysis of *Salinimonas sediminis* N102 (CP031769) shows various polysaccharide transporter, receptor and metabolic systems

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Similarly, oxidase- and catalase-positive bacterium *Salinimonas sediminis* N102 has been isolated from deep-sea sediment capable of optimal growth at 28 °C (temperature range, 4–40 °C), pH 7.0–7.5 (pH range, 6.0–9.0), 3–4% (w/v) NaCl (salt tolerance range, 2–15%), optimum pressure for growth 10 MPa (pressure tolerance up to 70 MPa). Like *Thiobacimonas profunda* JLT2016, strain N102 possess various metabolism and systems involved activities such as iron-siderophore sensory and receptor system, iron acquisition and various carbohydrate metabolism systems (**Figure 1**). Process optimization at laboratory scale generates potent exopolysaccharide for applications in food (as gels, thickening agent, food, preserver, and food stabilizing agent) and in agriculture (as an absorber for removal and accumulation of heavy metal ions, formation of metallic complexes, agents helps in quorum sensing and as a flocculating agent for municipal sludge treatment/removal of pollutants) (Korc and Varga, 2021; Berninger et al., 2021).

Uses of microbial potential in industries and for sustainable development

Marine microorganisms are well known for their potential biotechnological applications. Process optimization at laboratory scale generates potent exopolysaccharide for applications in food (as gels, thickening agent, food preservation, and food stabilizing agent) and in agriculture (absorber for removal and accumulation of heavy metal ions, formation of metallic complexes, helps in quorum sensing and flocculating agents for municipal sludge treatment/ removal of pollutants). Halophiles - piezohalopsychrophiles and piezoacidohyperthermophiles - such as *Micromonospora*, *Streptomyces*, *Rhodococcus marinonascens*, *Bathymodiolus septemdiemum*, *Thermococcus* sp., *Methanococcus janaschii*, *Halomonas* sp., *Calyptogen asoyoe*, *Thermovibrio ammonificans*, and others are capable of producing numerous bioactive polymers. Archaeal sterols, glycerol ethers, loihichelins, amphiphilic and ammonificins siderophores are among the metabolites produced by these polyextremophiles (Thornburg et al., 2010; Corinaldesi, 2015). These produce industrially important microbial metabolites especially exopolysaccharides (EPS) and siderophores those are useful in solubilization of trace elements. Production of these polymers by microorganisms may be initiated by quorum sensing. The variety of marine microorganisms capable of making EPS is an area that has received little attention of scientific community. In-depth investigation will shed a limelight for the discovery of biocatalytic molecules,

which may find ranges of applications in sustainable agriculture, preventing plant pest, increased crop production, removal of hazardous molecules from waste water and sewage, in therapeutics etc.

Capsular polymers are secreted by the marine EPS producer in their surroundings. The released EPS remain connected to the cell membrane via lipopolysaccharides (LPS), giving the producer colonies a slimy feel. The sluggish LPS may slowly make its way into the environment. Marine EPS is combined with other polysaccharides (chitosan, alginate) of bacterial origin to create host disease resistance. Moreover, it improves cell integrity, surface adhesion, nutrient trapping, and protects host cells from toxic compounds and detrimental bone-freezing conditions (Rekadwad and Khobragade, 2017). Therefore, exopolysaccharide producing bacteria (e.g. *Pseudomonas*) found in glacial ice have an ability to produce cryoprotective exopolysaccharide (Ali et al., 2020).

Such cold adapted marine microorganisms would have offering protection to marine chlorophyll producing cold-adapted flora in Antarctica. Additionally, many novel strains polysaccharide-secreting bacteria have been isolated from marine habitat (Table 1). As a result, researchers are increasingly focused on finding new marine bacteria in marine-environments, particularly in extremes such as marine habitats (Zhenming and Yan, 2004). The EPS proportion obviously varies between phytoplankton and bacteria, which may reflect the destiny of the ocean. Uronic acid, which makes up 20–50% of the total polysaccharide fraction in bacterial EPS, is a key component. Phytoplankton, on the other hand, has an EPS that is deficient in uronic acid. The negative (-) charge associated with COOH-groups of C₆H₁₀O₇ (uronic acid) in marine exopolysaccharide has been associated as the crucial factor of the complexified macromolecules with transition metals viz. Copper, Iron, Nickel, Zinc, Chromium, Gold, Cobalt, Manganese, Silver, Scandium, Mercury, Titanium, Vanadium, Platinum, Cadmium, Yttrium, Molybdenum, Rhodium, Tungsten, Ruthenium, Palladium, Niobium, Zirconium, Iridium, Osmium, Technetium, Hafnium, Copernicium, Roentgenium, Rhenium, Tantalum, Rutherfordium, Meitnerium, Seaborgium, Bohrium, Hassium, Darmstadtium and Dubnium. This property may have a substantial outcome on the long-term fortune and dilapidation of EPS in the ocean. Due to the difficulty in degrading bacterial

EPS as compared to eukaryotic EPS, it collects in marine environments (Zhang et al., 2015). It's still not clear what factors influence how readily bacterial extracellular polysaccharides (EPS) chelate heavy metal and their impact on various pathogens. Hence, isolation and characterization of both marine EPS-producing bacteria and their exo- mono- & polysaccharides using modern

techniques will help to understand the mechanism of exopolysaccharide action. Thus, this would offer for their use in agriculture as a suppressor of soil-borne plant pathogens, a tool for promoting plant growth, and a biocontrol agent against phytopathogens.

Table 1: Polysaccharide producing novel marine bacteria isolated between 2017-2021

Taxonomically valid name and strain number	Habitat	GenBank/EMBL/DDBJ accession number	Characteristics	Reference
<i>Alteromonas indica</i> IO390401	Surface seawater, Indian Ocean	MG852173, PYVY00000000	4.4 Mb chromosome, G+C content = 48.2 mol%	Lin et al., 2018
<i>Alteromonas oceani</i> S35	Deep sediment of hydrothermal vent	MF687202, NZ_RCUA00000000	Optimal growth at 28 °C, at pH 7.0–8.0 in media containing 2.0% (w/v) NaCl, GC Content 51.3 mol%	Jin et al., 2018
<i>Alteromonas lipolytica</i> JW12	Surface seawater	KX14648, MJIC00000000	Poly-bhydroxybutyrate producer, DNA GC Content 48.4 mol%	Shi et al., 2017
<i>Salinimonas sediminis</i> N102	Deep-sea sediment sample	MH816968, CP031769	oxidase- and catalase-positive, optimal growth at 28 °C (range, 4–40 °C), pH 7.0–7.5 (range, 6.0–9.0), 3–4%(w/v) NaCl (range, 2–15%), optimum pressure for growth 10 MPa, pressure tolerance up to 70 MPa	Cao et al., 2018
<i>Alteromonas aestuariivivens</i> JDTF-113	Tidal flat	NR_157790 / KY497472	Optimum growth at 30 °C, at pH 7.0–8.0, 2.0 % (w/v) NaCl	Park et al., 2017
<i>Alteromonas pelagimontana</i> 5.12	Southwest Indian Ridge	LT593862, CP052766	Oxidase- and catalase-positive, optimum growth at 35 C, at pH 6.0, salt requirement 3.5 % (w/v) NaCl, DNA G+C content 46.1 mol%	Sinha et al., 2017
<i>Alteromonas alba</i> 190	Seawater of the West Pacific Ocean	MG856904, PVNP00000000	Optimum temperature 30 °C, range 4–40 °C, optimum pH 6.5, pH range 5.5–10.5, optimum salt concentration, 2%, salt tolerance limit between 0.5–12.5% (w/v) NaCl, DNA–DNA hybridization value 53.8%, DNA G+C content 48.7 mol%	Sun et al., 2019
<i>Falsibacillus albus</i> GY10110	Mangrove soil	MH13531, RCVZ00000000	Temperature 15–37 C (optimum, 28 C), Salt tolerance at 0–3 %(w/v) (Optimum, 1 %) NaCl, pH range 6.0–9.0 (optimum, pH 7.0), DNA G+C content 42.3 mol%	Shi et al., 2019
<i>Paenibacillus oceani</i> IB182363	Surface seawater	MN911320, NZ_JACXJA00000000	pH 5.0–9.5 (optimum, pH 7-8), 20–40 °C (optimum, 30 °C), NaCl tolerance 1–8% (w/v with optimum, 2–4%, DNA G+C content 54.5mol%	Chen et al., 2021

CONCLUSION

Salt-loving marine exopolysaccharide producing bacteria are mostly belonging the mesophilic to the psychrophilic range of temperature tolerance with some exceptions

such as thermophiles/ hyperthermophiles inhabiting hydrothermal vents and hot springs. These bacteria possess the inherent ability to produce exopolysaccharides either in response to hostile conditions or in response to signalling molecules.

The later response suggests that polysaccharides secreted by marine bacteria would have offered benefits to signalling flora and nourishes its surrounding. Therefore, exploitation of these real microbial slick gems will offer benefits in various sectors for sustainable developments in agriculture, the environment and in health sectors.

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